

Development and Characterization of Jute, Sisal and their Hybrid Composite Materials with Coconut Shell Biochar

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Abstract:

Natural fiber-reinforced hybrid composites offer a sustainable alternative to synthetic materials due to their biodegradability, cost-effectiveness, and good mechanical properties. This study investigates jute-sisal hybrid composites supplemented with filler made of coconut shell biochar and fibers that have been alkali-treated. Alkali treatment improves fiber-matrix bonding by enhancing surface roughness and reducing impurities. Coconut shell biochar improves thermal stability, strength, and moisture resistance. The study included comprehensive testing of the composites, focusing on their thermal behavior, moisture absorption, and mechanical strength indicators—tensile, flexural, and impact. Results showed improved interfacial adhesion and mechanical properties due to alkali treatment, while biochar increased durability and thermal resistance. These bio-based composites are promising for applications in automotive parts, lightweight structures, and sustainable packaging, promoting the development of environmentally friendly polymer materials.

Keywords: *Alkali treatment, Coconut shell biochar, Eco-friendly materials, Mechanical performance, Natural fiber-reinforced composites*

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1. Introduction

Natural fiber-reinforced hybrid composites are gaining an edge because of their sustainability, cost-effectiveness, and excellent mechanical properties. In addition to their high strength-to-weight ratio, biodegradability, and renewable nature, jute and sisal fiber reinforced composites stand out as particularly noteworthy [1, 2 & 3]. Alkali treatment is known to promote fiber-matrix adhesion by eliminating surface contaminants and increasing interfacial bonding, resulting in improved mechanical characteristics [4]. Alkali treatment reduces the rate of water absorption in jute and sisal fibers by eliminating the principal hydrophilic components, hemicellulose and lignin [5]. A study found that 5% NaOH-treated natural fibers absorbed less water than untreated fibers and also increases tensile strength when compared to untreated fibers [6]. Alkaline treatment with 5% NaOH has been found to increase the mechanical properties of sisal fibers and their composites [7].

The hydrophobic characteristic of biochar reduces the interaction between the composite and water, resulting in increased dimensional stability [8]. A study utilizing coconut shell biochar in hybrid composites found a substantial reduction in water absorption compared to composites without biochar [9]. The composites' tensile strength is increased by the use of coconut shell biochar as a filler. Coconut shell biochar, with its high lignin content, enhances fiber-matrix bonding and helps to transmit stress between the fibers and the matrix [10, 11].

In general, jute and sisal hybrid composites absorb water at

lower rates than single-fiber composites because of the hybridization effect, which makes the fibers' hydroxyl groups less accessible [12, 13]. However, the presence of coconut shell biochar further reduces water absorption by creating a more hydrophobic interface within the composite [14]. After being soaked in water, the mechanical properties of hybrid composites made of jute and sisal that contain biochar derived from coconut shells are preserved to a considerable degree [15, 16].

The use of jute and sisal fibers, along with the reinforcing action of coconut shell biochar, is projected to result in a composite material with improved mechanical, thermal, and durability properties [17]. These composites have potential applications in the automotive, construction, and packaging industries, providing a more sustainable alternative to synthetic fiber-reinforced composites [18, 19]. The purpose of this study is to assess the impact of alkali treatment and biochar incorporation on the hybrid composite's overall performance, hence providing insights into its structural and functional behavior.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Sisal fiber utilized in the research was procured by the Sisal Research Station (SRS), a facility under ICAR-CRIJAF based in Bamra, Sambalpur, India. Additionally, jute fiber has been procured from the Central Research Institute for Jute and Allied Fibres, West Bengal, India. Epoxy resin (Araldite LY 556) and hardener (Aradur HY 951) have been used in a mixing ratio of 10:1 (epoxy to hardener). Table 1 delineates the physical attributes and qualities of jute and sisal fibers. The biochar filler material derived from coconut

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shells used in the composite, has been synthesized at our university laboratory by pyrolysis process.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Treatment of fibers with alkali

The fibers of sisal and jute were manually cut into segments about 5 cm in length. To eliminate dust and other water-soluble particles, both fibers were initially washed in tap water and subsequently in distilled water. Thereafter, both fibers were immersed in a 5% NaOH solution in separate containers for four hours in ambient temperature. Subsequent to their removal from the NaOH solution, the jute and sisal were neutralized by undergoing four to five washes in tap water and two washes in distilled water. After being left at room temperature for 72 hours, they were dried for five hours at 70°C in a hot air oven.

2.2.2. Fabrication of Epoxy based jute, sisal and jute-sisal hybrid composite

Compression molding was employed for composite fabrication. The fibers were combined in a 50:50 weight ratio using a carding machine. A needle-punched non-woven machine was employed to produce a fiber web from the fiber mixture. The composite was fabricated using a mold measuring 270 mm in length, 270 mm in width, and 4 mm in height. The hybrid composites were prepared with varying volume fractions (reinforcement: matrix: filler, 54:46:0, 54:39:7, 54:36:10, 58:35:7, and 58:32:10). At room temperature, a mechanical stirrer was used to mix the epoxy resin and hardener in a 10:1 ratio. The bubbles generated during mixing were eliminated using a sonication bath chamber. For 24 hours, the prepreg was kept at room temperature. After that, it was cured for 20 minutes in a compression molding press set to 80°C and 6330 N/m². The samples were manufactured using the concurrent curing procedure.

Table 1: Name and composition of the produced composites

Composite Designation	Epoxy (vol %)	Fibre (vol %)	Biochar (vol %)	FVF %
S1	46	Jute -54	0	54
S2	46	Sisal - 54	0	54
S3	39	Jute & Sisal - 54	7	54
S4	35	Jute & Sisal - 58	7	58
S5	36	Jute & Sisal - 54	10	54
S6	32	Jute & Sisal - 58	10	58

3. Characterization of hybrid composites

3.1. Thermal analysis

This examination reveals the thermal stability, composition, and reactivity of a material. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) is a thermal analysis technique that utilizes a single instrument to simultaneously assess a sample. All samples underwent analysis using the Simultaneous Thermal

Analyzer (STA) 6000. The operational temperature range of this device is 15 to 1000 degrees Celsius.

3.2. Water absorption analysis

The water absorption test was conducted in compliance with the ASTM D 570-98 standard. Each composite sample was weighed and positioned in separate water tanks at ambient temperature. The examination persisted for five days. Every 24 hours, the specimens were extracted from the water, dried with a cotton towel, and then weighed individually using a high-precision balance.

$$Mt = \frac{Wt - Wo}{Wt} \times 100$$

The equilibrium moisture content of the sample was calculated using the previously given equation, where W_o and W_t represent the weight of the sample in its original and wet states, after soaking and drying, respectively. Ant denotes the percentage of moisture content at time t .

3.3. Mechanical properties

The tensile test was conducted in accordance with ASTM D 3039 utilizing an Instron 5966 apparatus. The test samples were cut with dimensions of 250 × 25 × 4 mm, and the testing was performed at a traverse velocity of 5 mm per minute. In compliance with the ASTM D790-03 standard, the Instron 5966 was used to conduct the composite samples' three-point bend tests. Test samples of 127 × 12.7 × 4 mm were slit for the experiment and test was conducted at a velocity of 2 mm/min. The Izod impact test was conducted on a notched specimen with a volume of 70 mm³. The impact velocity ranged from 0 to 400 meters per minute, and the potential energy varied from 0.5 to 25 joules. The test was conducted in accordance with ASTM D 256 utilizing standard Izod impact testing apparatus (model IT 504, Tinius Olsen, USA). For impact test, the samples measuring 65 × 12.7 × 4 mm were cut for the test. The mean energy received by each sample was accurately assessed using an impact tester with a capacity of 25 J.

3.4. Surface Analysis using Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM)

Composite samples were analyzed using a JEOL-JSM-7610F Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Analysis of TGA

The TGA results for jute-sisal hybrid fiber composites and pure epoxy-based composites exhibited notable disparities in their heat degradation behavior. The pure epoxy-based composite (S1) demonstrated a unidirectional deterioration process, with a T_{max} of 494.4°C and no residual mass at 880°C. The sisal fibre composite (S2) generates zero residues with a low deterioration temperature and average maximum temperature. The jute-sisal fibre hybrid composites (S3-S6) demonstrated a multi-stage deterioration process, with T_{max}

values between 453.1°C and 475.6°C. The residual weight at 880°C exhibits considerable variation across the hybrid composites, with values spanning from 0% to 12.5%. The incorporation of jute-sisal fibers into the epoxy matrix improved the thermal stability of the composite. The hybrid composites including biochar filler demonstrate elevated T_{max} values and residual weights in comparison to the pure epoxy-based composite.

Figure 1: The TGA analysis of the epoxy-based pure and hybrid composites containing jute-sisal fibre

Table 2: TGA results for jute-sisal fibre hybrid composites and pure epoxy-based composites

Sample	T_d	T_{max}	T_f	Residue
	(°C) ^a	(°C) ^b	(°C) ^c	
S1	382.3	494.4	880	0
S2	346.4	466.4	880	0
S3	376.6	475.6	880	12.5
S4	330.5	461.5	880	0.7
S5	361.8	453.1	880	8.4
S6	359.1	467.2	880	0

T_d The temperature at which deterioration begins.

T_{max} The highest rate of mass loss at this temperature.

T_f Highest temperature of final deterioration

4.2. Water absorption

All composite samples show an increasing trend in water absorption over time, indicating that they absorb moisture progressively. This is expected in natural fiber-reinforced composites due to their hydrophilic nature. S3 exhibits the highest water absorption over time, depicting that it has the most hydrophilic nature or weaker fiber-matrix adhesion. S5 shows the lowest absorption, revealing better resistance to moisture. The better water resistance is likely due to the better fiber-matrix bonding or hydrophobicity (e.g., biochar presence). S4 and S6 show moderate water absorption, meaning they may have decent fiber treatment or filler effects reducing water uptake. The rate of absorption is higher in the initial hours (24–72 hours) and slows down over time (from 96 to 120 hours), which is typical for fiber-reinforced

composites as they reach saturation. Alkali-treated fibers usually have lower water absorption due to improved bonding with the matrix. The biochar has been used as filler in certain samples; which may be the reason of reducing water absorption by increasing hydrophobicity. Poor adhesion may allow more water penetration, leading to higher absorption.

Figure 2: The water absorption percentage of the epoxy-based pure and hybrid composites containing jute-sisal fibre

4.3. Tensile strength

Figure 3: The tensile strength (a) and tensile modulus (b) of the epoxy-based hybrid composites containing jute-sisal fibre in dry and water-soaked conditions

The majority of samples exhibit a decrease in tensile strength when immersed in water. S6 and S3 composites exhibit the most significant decline in strength i.e. 21.51% & 19.63% respectively. Here the sample S5 (8.17%) and S1 (10.79%) exhibit comparatively minor declines in the strength. Sample S4 exhibits a marginal enhancement (1.54%) in tensile strength under damp conditions. This may result from structural alterations or enhanced inter-fiber adhesion in water. Exposure to water typically diminishes the material's integrity, resulting in reductions between 8% and 21%. Regarding tensile modulus, Sample S3 has the least decrease in strength (-0.09%), indicating that water has a negligible impact on it. Composite samples S5 and S6 exhibit the highest decline, demonstrating that water substantially diminishes their strength. S6 exhibits the highest dry strength; nevertheless, it undergoes a significant decline when saturated. The retention % can be calculated using the following formula derived from the data.

$$\text{Retention Percentage} = \frac{\text{Dry Strength}}{\text{Water Soaked Strength}} \times 100$$

The data shows that sample S3 retained 99.91% of its original strength, indicating it is least affected by water. Sample S5 retained only 84.72%, showing high vulnerability to water absorption. Most samples retained between 85% to 97% of their strength, but S5 and S6 composite revealed significant reduction.

4.4. Flexural strength

Figure 4: The flexural strength (a) and flexural modulus (b) of the epoxy-based hybrid composites containing jute–sisal fibre in dry and water-soaked conditions

The data of flexural strength shows a reduction in strength. Dry Strength of composites is higher on an average than Water Soaked Strength. Water soaking reduces the flexural strength significantly. The minimum strength occurs in S5 (62.4 MPa) under water-soaked conditions, while the maximum dry strength is in S6 (93.3 MPa).

Percentage Reduction=

$$\frac{\text{Dry Strength} - \text{Water Soaked Strength}}{\text{Dry Strength}} \times 100$$

The highest strength reduction occurs in S6 (32.2%), meaning it is most affected by water soaking. S4 and S5 also show high reductions (above 20%), suggesting these materials are vulnerable in wet conditions. The least affected sample is S1 (11.7%), indicating better resistance to water. Also after calculating the strength retention, the data generates that S1 (88.3%) retains the most strength, indicating that it performs well in wet conditions. S6 retains only 67.8% of its strength, making it the most affected by water. On an average, the samples retain about 79-88% of their dry strength.

With respect to modulus, Dry flexural modulus is significantly higher on an average compared to water-soaked conditions. Minimum modulus occurs in composites S2 (9042 MPa Dry, 8835 MPa Soaked). Maximum modulus occurs in S4 (14101 MPa Dry, 11593 MPa Soaked). S3 (1.5%) and S2 (2.3%) show the least reduction, indicating they are least affected by water. S5 (20.7%) experiences the highest drop, meaning water significantly reduces its modulus. S4 and S6 also show high reductions (both above 17%), indicating a notable effect of water exposure. S3 (98.5%) and S2 (97.7%) retain the most strength, making them more resistant to water exposure. S5 retains only 79.3%, showing it is the one most affected by water.

4.5. Impact strength

Figure 5: The impact strength of the epoxy-based pure and hybrid composites containing jute–sisal fibre in dry and water-soaked conditions

The figure 5 shows the results of hybrid composites impact strength in water soaked also in dry condition. The minimum impact strength occurs in S5 (30.06 KJ/m² Dry), while the maximum is in S3 (57.81 KJ/m² Dry). The highest water-

soaked impact strength is in S2 (65.85 KJ/m²). S5 (36.8%) and S2 (34.1%) shows the highest increase in impact strength after water soaking. S1 (-9.3%) is the most negatively affected, meaning water weakens its impact strength. S3 and S6 show very minimal changes (less than 1%). S5 (136.8%) and S2 (134.1%) gains the most impact resistance in water-soaked conditions. S1 retains only 90.7% of its impact strength, meaning it loses the most after water soaking. S3 and S6 retain nearly 100%, showing little effect of water absorption. It has been observed that jute fibre reinforced composite (S1) is lying out, because after water soaking its strength decreases. Otherwise all the samples with sisal fibre and sisal jute hybrid gains impact strength after water soaked condition.

4.6. Surface morphology analysis

The surface morphology of pure jute fibers often displays a coarse and uneven texture characterized by natural micro voids and fibrillation as illustrated in Figure 6 with (a) 10 μm, and (b) 100 μm magnification. It's existence of surface contaminants including lignin, hemicellulose, and wax. Also inadequate interfacial adhesion with polymer matrices resulting from elevated hydrophilicity. Pure sisal strands exhibit a smoother texture than jute, due to its improved crystallinity and elevated structural rigidity compared to jute. In the Jute-Sisal hybrid composite utilizing coconut shell biochar as filler, the biochar effectively occupies voids, hence diminishing fiber pull-out and enhancing adhesion. Enhanced interfacial bonding has been observed resulting from biochar's capacity to generate a textured matrix for superior mechanical interlocking. Biochar diminishes micro voids, resulting in enhanced strength and durability. Biochar boosts thermal resistance and diminishes deterioration.

5. Conclusion

The comprehensive characterization of pure jute (S1), pure sisal (S2), and hybrid jute–sisal (S3–S6) composites reinforced with coconut shell biochar reveals significant improvements in mechanical, thermal, and moisture resistance properties. Pure jute offered greater flexibility, while pure sisal contributed higher stiffness. The hybridization of jute and sisal effectively combined these properties, resulting in composites with superior tensile, flexural, and impact performance. The incorporation of coconut shell biochar played a critical role in enhancing fiber–matrix adhesion, reducing void content, and improving thermal stability by delaying degradation. FESEM analysis confirmed better interfacial bonding and minimized fiber pullout in biochar-reinforced composites. Additionally, biochar significantly reduced water absorption, enhancing the long-term durability of the composites under both dry and water-soaked conditions. Overall, hybrid jute–sisal composites with coconut shell biochar present a sustainable and high-performance alternative for applications demanding moisture resistance and mechanical strength, particularly in the automotive, marine, construction, and eco-friendly packaging industries.

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7. Data availability

Data validating the results of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable inquiry.

Figure 6: These are the FESEM micrographs of the pure and hybrid composites made with epoxy that comprise jute–sisal fibre

8. Declarations

All authors have accepted and agreed to submit this paper to the Journal of Textile Association; it has not been published and is not being considered for publication elsewhere.

9. Conflict of interest

The authors affirm that there are no conflicts of interest related to this research.

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